

12- Month PhD Report December 2021

PhD 16 - Codes4strains

Responsible Partner: Institut Pasteur

1. Summary

Aim

Whole genome sequencing allows the tracking of pathogenic strains and informs infection control, diagnostic and sometimes treatment strategies. To track strains globally, and as they spread between the environment, food, animals and humans, universal strain nomenclatures are necessary. The core genome Multilocus Sequence Typing (cgMLST) approach is an accurate, reproducible and portable strain genotyping method that underlies widely used strain nomenclatures, in which groups are generally determined by single-linkage clustering. However, cgMLST groups are unstable due to the possibility of group fusion upon subsequent sampling. Recently, a new coding approach named LIN (Life Identification Number) was introduced by Marakeby et al. (1). It provides a numerical code for each genome based on its similarity (estimated using the Average Nucleotide Identity, ANI) to the closest genome already encoded. As LIN codes are attributed to genome rather than groups, they are stable. A common feature of both approaches is that single linkage groups and LINcodes can be defined using several similarity cutoffs, in which case they inherently convey phylogenetic proximity information. cgMLST additionally provides, through the number of allelic mismatches among cgMLST profiles, intuitive human-understandable metrics of differences among strains involved in epidemiological events (e.g., '5 cgMLST allele differences'). The aim of the PhD project is to develop a novel genome-based genotyping approach taking the best of the two above classification approaches, *i.e.*, combining the advantages of cgMLST (discrimination, standardization) with those of the LIN code approach (complete stability). That is, we aim to develop and explore the strain classification utility of cgMLST-based LIN code (cgLINcodes) systems, where the pairwise distance is based on the number of allelic mismatches, rather than ANI. We also aim to compare the cgLINcodes approach with other existing classification approaches: the SNP address and multi-level single-linkage classifications (Multilevel Single Linkage, MLSL). We use *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (Kp) and *Escherichia coli* (Ec) as two important pathogens to develop and evaluate our approach.

Report on the period of January to December 2021

Before the reporting period, we had selected our pilot genome dataset for the pathogen Kp (December 2019, **D-PhD16-2.1**).

We developed procedures (bioinformatics, algorithmic) to follow our goal of a cgMLST-based LIN code systems. First, we generated cgMLST profiles from genomes, using defined schemes. To this aim, the choice and the evaluation of the cgMLST schemes was finalized, for Kp and Ec (**D-PhD16-3.1**).

As a second task, the development of the cgMLST-based LIN code algorithm has been defined and a bioinformatics implementation was developed in Python (**D-PhD16-3.2**).

During this reporting period, we have consolidated our analyses of LINcodes and their comparison with MLSL. We have developed a novel way to define the population structure of species, called MSTclust; we have optimized our inheritance algorithm to provide backwards compatibility of MLSL groups with previous nomenclature identifiers from 7-gene MLST; we have defined the optimal input order for LIN encoding; we have compared the ANI metric with the cgMLST metric; we devised a method to identify recombination in cgMLST data; we have incorporated the MLSL identifiers into the BIGSdb platform to make them publicly available; and have submitted for publication a manuscript on the cgLIN codes concept and its implementation in Kp with comparison with multi-level single-linkage classifications (**D-PhD16-4.1**).

References:

1. Marakeby, H. *et al.* A System to Automatically Classify and Name Any Individual Genome-Sequenced Organism Independently of Current Biological Classification and Nomenclature. *PLOS ONE* **9**, e89142 (2014).

2. Overview of the PhD project progress

The initial objectives proposed for the PhD project are the following:

- To define a collection of pilot dataset of genomes including published outbreak sets
- To develop the cgLINcode approach and compare with MLSL and SNPaddress approaches on large genomic datasets
- To simulate genomic evolution and use the three approaches to encode resulting evolved genomes; compare resulting codes with expectations
- To write publications on the cgLINcodes concept and implementation with comparison with MLSL and SNPaddress approaches
- To disseminate the cgLINcodes approach towards collaborating partner institutes and to evaluate this approach in one Health and Global Health contexts
- To write-up the PhD dissertation

The first two objectives have been achieved over the period September 2019 – December 2020. The second objective was divided into 4 subtasks: define the cgMLST schemes to be used for the two pathogens; collect a full dataset of public genomic sequences and scan them to define their cgMLST allelic profiles; development of the cgLINcodes algorithm; and create and/or analyze the SNPaddress database and compare cgLINcodes with MLST and SNPaddress approaches.

We have decided to leave the simulation out of the scope of the PhD work, as the data analysis of the real dataset is thorough enough for us to conclude that LIN codes and MLSL provide fully congruent results. Therefore, there is no point in simulating datasets to evaluate the differential performance of one against the other method. This is an unexpected outcome of our evaluation of a large dataset of 7060 Kp genomes.

The scheduled work that is not complete yet is the development and analysis of the SNPaddress approach for Kp. We are first finalizing the manuscript on cgLINcodes for Kp, as this is the most innovative development and the manuscript is already complex and long. We thus reserve the comparison with SNP address for the next period, or possibly for an ulterior project outside of the PhD work.

During this period, we have submitted for publication the manuscript on the cgLINcodes approach and posted it on bioRxiv.

The remaining objectives for the next period are (i) to disseminate this approach towards our partners and explore its practical implementation in a One Health context; and (ii) We also intend to apply the LIN code approach and the tools we developed (MSTclust and inheritance to nomenclature identifiers) to other pathogens, even though this was not initially planned.

3. Progress of the research performed in the PhD project and key scientific results

D4.1. Simulated dataset analysed

We have decided to leave the simulation out of the scope of the PhD work, as the data analysis of the real dataset is thorough enough for us to conclude that LIN codes and MLSL provide fully congruent results. Therefore, there is no point in simulating datasets to evaluate the differential performance of one against the other method. This abandoned DL is largely compensated by our additional DLs outlined below.

D4.2. Publication on the cgLIN codes concept and its implementation in Kp with comparison with multi-level single-linkage classifications

The publication is posted on bioRxiv and under review in a journal; The current version of the abstract of the publication is the following:

Sublineages within microbial species can differ widely in their ecology and pathogenicity, and their precise

definition is important in basic research and industrial or public health applications. Whereas the classification and naming of prokaryotes is unified at the species level and higher taxonomic ranks, universally accepted definitions of sublineages within species are largely missing, which introduces confusion in population biology and epidemiological surveillance.

Here we propose a broadly applicable genomic classification and nomenclature approach for bacterial strains, using the prominent public health threat *Klebsiella pneumoniae* as a model. Based on a 629-gene core genome multilocus sequence typing (cgMLST) scheme, we devised a dual barcoding system that combines multilevel single linkage (MLSL) clustering and life identification numbers (LIN). Phylogenetic and clustering analyses of >7,000 genome sequences captured population structure discontinuities, which were used to guide the definition of 10 infra-specific genetic dissimilarity thresholds. The widely used 7-gene multilocus sequence typing (MLST) nomenclature was mapped onto MLSL sublineages (threshold: 190 allelic mismatches) and clonal group (threshold: 43) identifiers for backwards nomenclature compatibility. The taxonomy is publicly accessible through a community-curated platform (<https://bigsdbs.pasteur.fr/klebsiella>), which also enables external users' genomic sequences identification.

The proposed strain taxonomy combines two phylogenetically informative barcodes systems that provide full stability (LIN codes) and nomenclatural continuity with previous nomenclature (MLSL). This species-specific dual barcoding strategy for the genomic taxonomy of microbial strains is broadly applicable and should contribute to unify global and cross-sector collaborative knowledge on the emergence and microevolution of bacterial pathogens.

D4.3. (NEW) A novel tool to define the population structure of species, called MSTclust

To profile the population structure, we developed MSTclust (<https://gitlab.pasteur.fr/GIPhy/MSTclust>) and used this tool to perform single linkage (SL) clustering of allelic profiles into partitions, at all possible thresholds t (from 0 to 629 allelic differences). SL clustering was applied on the pairwise distances among allelic profiles, defined as the number of allele mismatches normalized by the number of loci with alleles called in both profiles (therefore accounting for missing data). For each threshold t , the degree of clustering (goodness-of-fit of the clustering to the population) of the corresponding allelic profile partitioning was assessed by three different measures: (i) The overall average silhouette width S_t (2), which estimates the overall clustering quality based on maximizing inter-group distances and minimizing intra-group distances; (ii) the clustering robustness index in face of data subsampling, estimated by the Wallace index W_t (3); and (iii) The adjusted Rand index R_t (4,5) to assess the global concordance between the SL partitioning and those induced by any external classifications. For the application on Kp, we used as external classifications the 7-gene MLST sequence types, subspecies and species classifications.

D4.4. (NEW) Optimization of our inheritance algorithm to provide backwards compatibility of MLSL groups with 7-gene MLST

In order to attribute to each sublineage (SL) and clonal group (CG), an identifier that would maximally reflect the widely adopted 7-gene ST identifier of the corresponding isolates, we developed a set of naming rules that prioritize the most abundant ST observed among isolates of each group.

We briefly describe the process for the clonal groups (CG) level, and it would also apply in the same way for sublineages (SL). The data (e.g., a list of CG-ST pairs) can be formalized as a bipartite graph, in which each CG or ST are nodes, and each CG-ST pair is an edge. The weight of each edge is equal to the number of isolates sharing the corresponding CG and ST identifiers. Based on this representation, the algorithm will consist in following all edges in the input graph, in the order of decreasing weight. The approach prioritizes the most frequent ST/CG pairs of isolates, *i.e.*, those that are epidemiologically predominant, and thus naturally transfers to the CG nomenclature, the identifiers of the epidemiologically major STs. Rules were implemented to treat the cases of equality of representation of two or more STs connected to the same CG. Once all edges were removed from the graph, it may happen that some CGs were not yet named (for example, because the identifier of their unique corresponding ST was already attributed to another CG). For these orphan CGs, iteratively, the attributed

identifier corresponds to the maximal CG identifier already attributed, plus one. Finally, to highlight identifiers that were attributed with no reference to 7-gene MLST identifiers, their numbering was initiated at 10000.

D4.5. (NEW) Comparison of the ANI metric with the cgMLST metric

We compared ANI-based distances with the number of mismatches between cgMLST profiles (**Figure1**). While the ANI-based distances varied from 92.8% to 100%, the cgMLST distances varied from 0 to 100% (*i.e.*, 629 allele mismatches). Although both distributions had four to five modes, the first two modes of the ANI distance distribution, composed of inter-phylogroup strain comparisons, were at 93.5% to 95.5% ANI, whereas in the cgMLST distribution these distance pairs were centered around 2%, corresponding to the first mode of this distribution. In turn, whereas intra-species cgMLST distances varied from 5% to 100%, the range was only 98% to 100% for ANI values.

Figure 1. The distribution of pairwise distances of 7060 genomes of *Kp* based on Average Nucleotide Identity (ANI) and cgMLST. (A) Each point represents a pair of distances between two strains, the X-axis the distance cgMLST and the Y-axis the distance ANI, the distributions are shown on the outside of the graph. We have colored the points corresponding to intergroup and intragroup distance. (B) Distribution of cgMLST pairwise distance. (C) Distribution of ANI pairwise distance.

The ANI metric was not designed to define the similarity of closely related genomes, such as those of strains within species; for example, high similarity values (e.g. 99.9990% and 99.9991%) are not intuitive to compare. In addition, the ANI metric is non-reciprocal, is highly dependent on comparison parameters, and is sensitive to sequencing or assembly artifacts. This shortfalls of the ANI metric lead to imprecision and non-reproducibility that are particularly impactful for comparisons between very similar genomes.

In contrast, the metric based on a cgMLST scheme, comprising 629 highly conserved and syntenic genes, was appropriate to reveal discontinuities that are relevant for strain nomenclature purposes.

D4.6. (NEW) Designed a method to identify recombination in cgMLST profiles

Horizontal transfer of large portions of the genome can occur among isolates belonging to distinct KpSC phylogroups (6). Additionally, MLST or cgMLST alleles may have been transferred horizontally from non-KpSC members, for example *E. coli*. For the purpose of phylogeny-based classification, we excluded such hybrid genomes. To define genomes that result from large inter-phylogroup recombination events, we leveraged our gene-by-gene approach to define an original strategy, outlined briefly here: we first attempted to determine for each allele of each locus, its KpSC phylogroup of origin; we then quantified a phylogroup homogeneity index of each genome by simply summing phylogroup origins of individual loci over the 629 scgMLSTv2 loci. The index was defined as the number of loci in the predominant phylogroup, divided by the number of alleles called in the profile. We then established a distribution of the phylogroup homogeneity indices to define genomes as having a hybrid origin.

D4.7. (NEW) Integration of MLST identifiers into the BIGSdb platform to make them publicly available

The MLST nomenclature was incorporated into the Institut Pasteur *K. pneumoniae* MLST and whole genome MLST database (<https://bigsdb.pasteur.fr/klebsiella>). For this purpose, classification schemes and attached information fields were implemented as a novel BIGSdb functionality in BIGSdb version 1.21.0. The cgMLST profile of all isolates with less than 30 missing cgMLST-629 alleles were assigned to a core genome sequence type (cgST), and these were grouped into single-linkage partitions at the 10 defined mismatch levels. For SL and CG levels, a custom classification group field (named SL or CG within the system) was populated with 7-gene MLST inherited identifiers. All cgMLST profiles and their corresponding classification identifiers were made available for public use.

To allow users to easily identify *K. pneumoniae* isolates, a profile matching functionality was developed, allowing to search for cgMLST profiles related to a query genome sequence. This was implemented and is available from the website sequence query page (<https://bigsdb.readthedocs.io/en/latest/administration.html#scheme-profile-clustering-setting-up-classification-schemes>). This functionality returns the classification identifiers (including MLST-inherited clonal group and sublineage identifiers) of the cgMLST profile that is most closely related to the query genomic sequence, along with its number of mismatches compared to the closest profile.

References:

1. Marakeby, H. *et al.* A System to Automatically Classify and Name Any Individual Genome-Sequenced Organism Independently of Current Biological Classification and Nomenclature. *PLOS ONE* **9**, e89142 (2014).
2. Rousseeuw, P. J. Silhouettes: A graphical aid to the interpretation and validation of cluster analysis. *J. Comput. Appl. Math.* **20**, 53–65 (1987).
3. Wallace, D. L. A Method for Comparing Two Hierarchical Clusterings: Comment. *J. Am. Stat. Assoc.* **78**, 569–576 (1983).
4. Hubert, L. & Arabie, P. Comparing partitions. *J. Classif.* **2**, 193–218 (1985).
5. Carriço, J. A. *et al.* Illustration of a Common Framework for Relating Multiple Typing Methods by Application to Macrolide-Resistant *Streptococcus pyogenes*. *J. Clin. Microbiol.* **44**, 2524–2532 (2006).
6. Holt, K. E. *et al.* Genomic analysis of diversity, population structure, virulence, and antimicrobial resistance in *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, an urgent threat to public health. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* **112**, E3574–81 (2015).

4. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

PhD Project Reference	Deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Actual Delivery Date	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
	D-PhD16-3.4	SNapperDB Kp implemented for full dataset	M36		M48	We did not create SNapperDB for the pathogen Kp yet. We are finalizing the manuscript on cgLINcodes for Kp first.
	D-PhD16-4.1	Simulated dataset analysed	M42		M48	Priority to writing the publication on the cgLINcodes approach
	D-PhD16-4.2	Publication on LINcode approach and comparison with cgMLST and SNP address approaches	M48		M48	Submitted and under Review
	D-PhD16-4.3	A novel tool to define the population structure of species, called MSTclust		M40		
	D-PhD16-4.4	Optimization of our inheritance algorithm to provide backwards compatibility of MLST groups with 7-gene MLST		M42		
	D-PhD16-4.5	Comparison of the ANI metric with the cgMLST metric		M42		
	D-PhD16-4.6	Designed a method to identify recombination in cgMLST		M40		
	D-PhD16-4.7	Integration of MLST identifiers into the BIGSdb platform to make them publicly available		M42		

Milestones

PhD Project Reference	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from Annual Work Plan	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
	M-PhD16-3.3	SNapperDB databases set-up for both pathogens	M36	Yes/no		Yes for Ec; not yet for Kp
	M-PhD16-4.1	Simulations completed	M42	No		Priority to writing the publication on the cgLINcodes approach
	M-PhD16-4.2	Publication submitted	M48	Yes/No		Submitted and under Review
	D-PhD16-4.3	A novel tool to define the population structure of species, called MSTclust	M40	Yes		
	D-PhD16-4.4	Optimization of our inheritance algorithm to provide backwards compatibility of MLSL groups with 7-gene MLST	M42	Yes		
	D-PhD16-4.5	Comparison of the ANI metric with the cgMLST metric	M42	Yes		
	D-PhD16-4.6	Designed a method to identify recombination in cgMLST	M40	Yes		
	D-PhD16-4.7	Integration of MLSL identifiers into the BIGSdb platform to make them publicly available	M42	Yes		

5. Soft skills and Continuing Professional Development training

None in this reporting period.

6. Publications and additional outputs

Publications

In addition to the main project, I also contribute to side projects. The PhD host lab comprises the National Reference Center for Corynebacteria of the diphtheriae complex (i.e., *C. diphtheriae*, *C. ulcerans* and phylogenetically related species; <https://www.pasteur.fr/fr/sante-publique/CNR/les-cnr/corynebacteries-du-complexe-diphtheriae>). It thereby collects and characterizes all potentially toxigenic strains identified in French metropolitan area and overseas territories, since 11 years. This unique collection of isolates and the associated clinical and epidemiological data has been an essential resource for various related projects.

I have been interested in and contributed to a few of these projects, including the study of the diversity and evolution of *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* and the computational research of antimicrobial resistance. Below is a list of articles where I have made contributions:

Hennart, M., Guglielmini, J., Maiden, M.C., Jolley, K.A., Criscuolo, A. and Brisse, S., 2021. A dual barcoding approach to bacterial strain nomenclature: Genomic taxonomy of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* strains. bioRxiv 2021.07.26.453808. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.07.26.453808>

Guglielmini J., Hennart M., Badell E., Toubiana J., Criscuolo A., Brisse S., 2021. Genomic epidemiology and strain taxonomy of *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*. *Journal of Clinical Microbiology*. 0(ja):JCM.01581-21.

Badell, E., Alharazi, A., Criscuolo, A., Almoayed, K.A.A., Lefrancq, N., Bouchez, V., Guglielmini, J., Hennart, M., Carmi-Leroy, A., Zidane, N., Pascal-Perrigault, M., Lebreton, M., Martini, H., Salje, H., Toubiana, J., Dureab, F., Dhabaan, G., Brisse, S., Rawah, A.A., Aldawla, M.A., Al-Awdi, E.M., Al-Moalmy, N.M., Al-Shami, H.Z., Al-Somainy, A.A., 2021. Ongoing diphtheria outbreak in Yemen: a cross-sectional and genomic epidemiology study. *Lancet Microbe* 0. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2666-5247\(21\)00094-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2666-5247(21)00094-X) (GOLD, 4300 EUROS)

Badell, E., Hennart, M., Rodrigues, C., Passet, V., Dazas, M., Panunzi, L., Bouchez, V., Carmi-Leroy, A., Toubiana, J., Brisse, S., 2020. *Corynebacterium rouxii* sp. nov., a novel member of the diphtheriae species complex. *Res. Microbiol.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resmic.2020.02.003>; PMID: 32119905 (GREEN, 12 months).

Hennart, M., Panunzi, L.G., Rodrigues, C., Gaday, Q., Baines, S.L., Barros-Pinkelng, M., Carmi-Leroy, A., Dazas, M., Wehenkel, A.M., Didelot, X., Toubiana, J., Badell, E., Brisse, S., 2020. Population genomics and antimicrobial resistance in *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*. *Genome Med.* 12, 107. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13073-020-00805-7>; PMID: 33246485; PMCID: PMC7694903. (GOLD OPEN ACCESS, 3000 EUROS)

Additional output

Proceedings of the 2nd Annual Scientific Meeting of the One Health European Joint Programme on Foodborne Zoonoses, Antimicrobial Resistance and Emerging Threats. Online meeting, May 27th - 29th, 2020, page 71.

Deliverables of Codes4strains project (Part1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4471354>

Deliverables of Codes4strains project (Part2). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5284876>

7. Remarkable outcomes

Our publication on the cgLIN codes concept and its implementation in *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in comparison with multi-level single-linkage classifications should soon be available on bioRxiv.

8. Impact & relevance

The project will define, implement and evaluate a novel bioinformatics strategy to classify and name strains within pathogenic bacteria, from the level of deep subspecific lineages down to shallower levels of diversity that differentiate epidemiological related strains from non-related ones. It will be first tested on Ec and Kp, two important ubiquitous 'One Health' pathogens. However, the general applicability of the approach means that in the future, the classification and nomenclature of strains of other pathogens could benefit from the PhD project outcomes.

By facilitating in the future, communication on bacterial strains across sectors and countries, the project is highly relevant to multiple topics and objectives of One Health EJP: antibiotic resistance clonal dissemination, emerging pathogens, cross-sector transmission, public health and basic microbiology integration.

The project will deliver a novel nomenclature system of bacterial pathogens genomes that will be stable by design, unlike existing systems based on SNPs and cgMLST single linkage groupings. This has a far-reaching impact on possibilities to integrate efforts of agencies (e.g., at the international levels, ECDC, EFSA, PulseNet international) to detect, monitor, understand and control the spread of pathogens.

9. Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics Advisors

Requirement (from ethical reviewers)	Measures and actions taken
None	None

10. Impact of COVID-19 crisis on the project

Tasks or Subtasks			Milestones and Deliverables				Associated budget	
Name of Task or Subtask	End date according to AWP 2020	Expected end date due to crisis	Associated Milestone or Deliverable	Deadline according to AWP 2020	New proposed deadline	Reason for delay	Budget that will not be spent	Budget that will be spent with delay

Comments: No impact, as our bioinformatics work was not affected.

11. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of PhD supervisor(s)	No
Loss of technical training staff delaying progress of the work	No
Delay in work plan execution	No
Conflicts between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Lack of commitment between the collaborative partners that support the PhD	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	No
Poor working relationships within the PhD project team	No
Change in PhD student circumstances requiring temporary leave	No
Other risks (please describe)	None

Additional information: None

12. Interactions with on-going JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant projects or initiatives such as national action plans (AMR, Zoonoses etc.), OHEJP stakeholders, national and international surveillance programmes.

The novel method developed in the PhD project will find natural dissemination ways via the existing networks of collaborations in which the main investigators are involved: MedVetKlebs (just finished JRP), KlebNET, SpARK, kleb-GAP; Nor-Kleb-Net for Kp (see MedVetKlebs final report) and KlebNET-GSP (funded by BMGF); and Ec surveillance networks and national and international levels (e.g., French NRC & NRL @Pasteur and ANSES; ECDC; PulseNet international).

The novel nomenclature system will be compared with existing nomenclatures (dictionaries of nomenclature correspondence between LIN codes and current SNP/cgMLST nomenclatures for wider communication and backwards-compatibility) and will need in the future to be integrated in existing platforms that serve nomenclatures of bacterial strains (e.g., SnapperDB, EnteroBase, BIGSdb-Oxford and PulseNet international for *E. coli*; BIGSdb-Pasteur for *K. pneumoniae*). Future interactions with 'dev-op' specialists (application developers) will be established with free software such as EnteroBase, BIGSdb and Innuendo; or commercial software such as BioNumerics or SeqSphere.

Following the writing of the first draft of our publication on the cgLIN codes concept and its implementation in Kp with comparison with multi-level single-linkage classifications, Martin M.C. Maiden and Keith A. Jolley became aware of it and were interested in applying our methods on other pathogens of interest to the One Health perspective (*Campylobacter*) or Clinical/Antimicrobial resistance (*N. gonorrhoeae*)

13. List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	<i>"Journées Boris Ephrussi" 2021</i>		
Date:	Poster : A new approach for naming bacterial strains, combining cgMLST and LIN codes May 27 th -28 th 2021		
Place:	Digital Conference		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>		<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	Yes
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>		<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	
<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	Yes
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>		<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			

Name of the activity:	<i>OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021 – poster presentation</i>		
Date:	<i>09-11 June 2021</i>		
Place:	<i>Online</i>		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	<i>Yes / No</i>		<i>Yes / No</i>
<i>Organisation of a Conference</i>	<i>NO</i>	<i>Participation to a Conference</i>	<i>Yes</i>
<i>Organisation of a Workshop</i>	<i>NO</i>	<i>Participation to a Workshop</i>	<i>NO</i>
<i>Press release</i>	<i>NO</i>	<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	<i>NO</i>
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>	<i>NO</i>	<i>Video/Film</i>	<i>NO</i>
<i>Exhibition</i>	<i>NO</i>	<i>Brokerage Event</i>	<i>NO</i>
<i>Flyer</i>	<i>NO</i>	<i>Pitch Event</i>	<i>NO</i>
<i>Training</i>	<i>NO</i>	<i>Trade Fair</i>	<i>NO</i>
<i>Social Media</i>	<i>NO</i>	<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	<i>NO</i>
<i>Website</i>	<i>NO</i>	<i>Other</i>	<i>NO</i>
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>	<i>NO</i>		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categoriesS			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>	<i>550+</i>	<i>Media</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>Industry</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>Investors</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>Civil Society</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>Customers</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>General Public</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>Other</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>Policy Makers</i>	<i>0</i>		

